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PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 21

Issue 4

Pages: 490-493

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1976

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12594042

Manuscript Accepted: 02-27-2024

Assessment on the Implementation of Project POD-LAC at Simona National High School

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Abstract

This paper discussed the evaluation of the implementation of Project POD-LAC Session at Simona National High School, Taytay Sub-office, during the School Year 2023-2024. A descriptive research method was employed utilizing a researcher-made questionnaire checklist sent through Google Forms for data gathering. Twenty-six (26) teachers at the school served as the respondents whose performance was analyzed and who evaluated the program's implementation. Based on the research findings, there is a significant increase in the performance rating of the teachers after being engaged in Project POD-LAC Sessions, as reflected in their IPCRF rating for the previous and current school year. In addition, the teachers evaluated the program that is relevant to its objective, mechanism, monitoring, and evaluation as Much Agree as they believe that it has goal congruent to the guidelines, effective process or procedures, and established way of monitoring and evaluation each session and the outputs. They also suggested to include demonstration teaching in the LAC Session and utilized Google Drive for their outputs.

Keywords: *LAC session, teachers, IPCRF*

Introduction

Teachers are the key component to shape the educational landscape and prepare every generation for their future endeavors. The educational systems are constantly developing to teach suitable and appropriate skills that are necessary for the students to thrive and succeed in this ever-changing world.

As shown by Bangayan-Manera et al. (2020), teachers' performances will be assessed if they will be evaluated. Evaluation involves looking through their learning goals, feed back, and discussion they are trying to make inside the classroom. By understand their strengths and weaknesses, the schools can improve teaching by addressing the problem or any issues that will be encountered upon assessing them.

The country uses the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) to assess the performances of the teachers against set goals (Department of Education, 2015). This system has four stages: planning, monitoring, evaluation, and development. But recently, a new policy under the DepEd Memorandum No. 008 in 2023, the teacher evaluation should be guided with the 37 indicators of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) through the school years.

Since these guidelines are new again for all teachers, it seems very difficult for them to gather the necessary documents as they do not comprehensively understand the guidelines. In addition, due to the late release of the memorandum, teachers find it hard to accomplish within the given period of time considering the other tasks and responsibilities that the teachers shall perform especially in this time of new normal system.

Relatively, Simona National High School, Project POD-LAC Sessions was initiated and implemented with aim of preparing and accomplishing the portfolio of teachers for 2023 RPMS-IPCRF. This basically aimed to provide technical assistance to the teachers in their preparation of Means of Verification (MoVs) or pertinent documents needed in all the objectives of RPM-IPCRF to be compiled in their portfolio.

Teachers were engaged in series of School Learning Action Cell Sessions about the objectives based on the current guidelines. The Department of Education created the Learning Action Cells (LAC) in 2016 where teachers meet each other to discuss and solve the problems or issues they face or may arise inside the classroom. Thus, this program merely provided an avenue for teachers in completing their portfolio with ease and ahead of time.

The researcher, as the school head, conducted this study to determine the evaluation of the teachers on the implementation of the project and identify their perceptions as regards the things to be enhanced for further improvement of the project.

Research Questions

This study focused on the evaluation of the implementation of Project POD-LAC Session at Simona National High School, Taytay Sub-office, during the School Year 2023-2024. Particularly, the researcher aimed to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the performance ratings of the teacher-respondents as reflected in their IPCRF for the previous and current school year?
2. What is the evaluation of the teacher respondents on the implementation of Project POD-LAC with respect to:
 - 2.1. objectives;
 - 2.2. mechanism; and

- 2.3. monitoring and evaluation?
3. What are the suggestions of the teacher-respondents to further improve the program?
4. What Action Plan can be proposed for the implementation of Project POD-LAC in the next school year?

Literature Review

The Department of Education (DEpEd) established the Learnig Action Cells (LAC) to give support to the ongoing professional development of the teachers (Luistro, 2016). These groups focus primarily in various areas of teaching like the student diversity, assessing lessons against the curriculum standards, adapting the curriculum into local contexts, and addressing the concerns of the teachers about the teaching content and methods (Avalos, 2011). Moreover, this approach aligns with the concept of Continuing Professional Development (CPD) that aims to keep the teachers' skills, practices, styles, and methods into up-to-date.

LAC, on the one hand, is valuable because they help teachers in developing their complex skills needed in the 21st century such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and creativity which are essential especially in this evolving educational landscape (Parker et al., 2016). These skills are also crucial for teachers to achieve their own development, and also a key factor to make the students increase their academic achievement.

However, in the studies of Dizon et al. (2018), Mamauag and Antonio (2022), and Ormilla (2021), they have identified that there are concerns with the implementation of the separate Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS). These concerns identified the problem in accountability, where the teachers feel that they are not being evaluated properly..

Methodology

Respondents

The researcher used total-enumeration sampling technique in choosing the respondents. The total enumeration sampling is a type of research method where every single member of a small and well-defined group is being examined (Arnab, 2017). This sampling method was the suitable to this study since all the twenty-six (26) teachers were involved in the conduct of Project POD-LAC Sessions.

Procedure

The proponent utilized a researcher-made questionnaire-checklist to gather the needed data for this study. After completing the research proposal, she sought permission from the supervisors to conduct the study. With the permission, she informed the target respondents regarding the aim of the research. She then crafted the research instrument using the Google Form. The link of this online version of the instrument was given to all the teacher-respondents. The researcher herself monitored the submission of the responses to ensure the completeness. In addition, the researcher analyzed the RPMS-IPCRF as regards the performance rating of the respondents from previous and current school year.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage of performance rating of the teacher-respondents for the School Years 2022-2023 and 2023-2024.

Table 1. *Performance Rating of Techer-Respondents during SY 2022-2023 and 2023-2024*

IPCRF Rating	SY 2022-2023		SY 2023-2024	
	F	%	F	%
4.500- 5.000 (Outstanding)	3	11.54%	7	26.93%
4.000-4.499 (Very Satisfactory)	10	38.46%	15	57.69%
3.500-3.999 (Very Satisfactory)	13	50%	4	15.38%
Total	26	100%	26	100%

It can be seen on the table that in the during the SY 2022-2023 13 or 50 percent of the teacher-respondents obtained an IPCRF rating ranging from 3.500-3.999 which has adjectival rating of Very Satisfactory, 10 or 38.46 percent belong to range of 4.000-4.499 equal to adjectival rating of Very Satisfactory, and 3 or 11.54 percent who garnered Outstanding rating from 4.500-5.000. Meanwhile, during the SY 2023-2024 the numbers of teachers with Very Satisfactory ratings ranging from 4.000-4.499 is 15 or 57.59 percent, Outstanding rating ranging from 4.500-5.000 is 7 or 26.93 percent, and Very Satisfactory rating ranging from 3.500-3.999 is 15.38 percent.

The data reflect that the teachers from Simona National High School performed their tasks as educators very well and achieved the set objectives and standards as indicated in the guidelines of IPCRF-RPMS. It is important to note that the current school year shows significant increase in the number of teachers who gained Outstanding and Very satisfactory rating that is near to the highest rating.

This implies that the implementation of Project POD-LAC Session aided the teachers in properly preparing their documents need for the performance evaluation. Likewise, the program elevated their performances as evidently shown in their portfolio.

Tables 2 presented the evaluation of the teacher-respondents on the implementation of Project POD-LAC Sessions with respect to the objectives.

It can be glanced on the table that the teacher-respondents evaluated the implementation of Project POD-LAC Sessions with respect to objectives as Much Agree with the obtained overall mean of 3.70. This means that the teachers concurred to the idea that the project has set targets cognizant with the prescribed guidelines which had driven them to have good performance.

Table 2. Evaluation of Teacher-Respondents on Project POD-LAC Session with Respect to Objectives

<i>Objectives</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. Project POD-LAC Session has attainable objectives.	3.70	Much Agree
2. The goal of the project is aligned with the guidelines of IPCRF-RPMS.	3.90	Much Agree
3. Teachers are well-oriented about the target in each session.	3.70	Much Agree
4. The Objectives help the proponent and the teacher accomplish the expected output.	3.40	Much Agree
5. The project motivated more the teachers to prepare their portfolio.	3.80	Much Agree
Overall Mean	3.70	Much Agree

It implies that Project POD-LAC has an end view that is beneficial to all the teachers as they deal with all the objectives of IPCRF-RPMS.

Tables 3 presents the evaluation of the teacher-respondents on the implementation of Project POD-LAC Sessions with respect to mechanism.

Table 3. Evaluation of Teacher-Respondents on Project POD-LAC Session with Respect to Mechanism

<i>Mechanism</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. Project POD-LAC Session has a clear process	3.40	Much Agree
2. The discussions are sufficient and helpful to all teachers in preparing the portfolio.	3.60	Much Agree
3. Teachers are properly guided on the procedures of the submission of outputs.	3.70	Much Agree
4. Teachers are engaged in collaborative and reflective learning experiences.	3.30	Much Agree
5. The project allows the teachers to prepare their documents with ease.	3.50	Much Agree
Overall Mean	3.50	Much Agree

It can be gleaned on the table that the teacher-respondents evaluated the implementation of Project POD-LAC Sessions with respect to mechanism as Much Agree with the obtained overall mean of 3.50. This indicates that the teacher-respondents believe that the project has effective framework of procedures.

It implies that Project POD-LAC is conducted with well-defined process which engages the teachers in group discussions allowing them to prepare their documents properly as required in each session.

Table 4 presents the evaluation of the teacher-respondents on the implementation of Project POD-LAC Sessions with respect to monitoring and evaluation.

Table 4. Evaluation of Teacher-Respondents on Project POD-LAC Session with Respect to Monitoring and Evaluation

<i>Monitoring and Evaluation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>
1. The project leader and members religiously monitored the conduct of every session.	4.00	Much Agree
2. The team conducts risk analysis relative to every aspect of the program.	3.60	Much Agree
3. The team identify plans for the continuous improvement of the program.	3.70	Much Agree
4. Teachers are involved in monitoring and evaluating their outputs.	3.20	Much Agree
5. The proponent provides periodic and timely feedback on the conduct of each session.	3.90	Much Agree
Overall Mean	3.68	Much Agree

It can be seen on the table that the teacher-respondents evaluated the implementation of Project POD-LAC Sessions with respect to monitoring and evaluation as Much Agree with the obtained overall mean of 3.68. This suggests that the program, with the leadership of the proponent includes established monitoring and evaluation system in its process.

It implies that Project POD-LAC as good way of identifying the success indicators of the programs and its areas for improvement. Likewise, the monitoring and evaluation allows the teachers to produce the target outputs they needed for each objective of the IPCRF-RPMS.

Suggestions of the Teacher-respondents

The following were the suggestions and recommendations of the teacher-respondents when they ask about how the program would be further improved.

The program is very timely and relevant. It would have been better if the LAC Session will start as early as the second month of the School Year.

Project POD-LAC allows us to collaboratively work and prepare our documents. It would be better if demonstration teaching will be included for deeper understanding.

Outputs of teachers should be immediately checked, and feedback should be given at once.

Utilize Google Drive for the outputs for easier access and retrieval of the documents.

Plans for Dissemination and Utilization

<i>DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES</i>	<i>March</i>	<i>April</i>	<i>May</i>	<i>June</i>	<i>July</i>	<i>August</i>
1. Finalization of Research						
2. Presentation of Results to school						
3. Submission and Presentation of Results in the Sub-office						
4. Presentation to Division for possible adaption						

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